

Enhance Image Transmission Based on DWT with Pixel Interleaver

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Abstract—The recent growth of using multimedia transmission over wireless communication systems, have challenges to protect the data from lost due to wireless channel effect. Images are corrupted due to the noise and fading when transmitted over wireless channel, in wireless channel the image is transmitted block by block. Due to severe fading, entire image blocks can be damaged. The aim of this paper comes out from need to enhance the digital images at the wireless receiver side. Proposed Boundary Interpolation (BI) Algorithm using wavelet, have been adapted here used to reconstruction the lost block in the image at the receiver depend on the correlation between the lost block and its neighbors. New Proposed technique by using Boundary Interpolation (BI) Algorithm using wavelet with Pixel interleaver has been implemented. Pixel interleaver work on distribute the pixel to new pixel position of original image before transmitting the image. The block lost through wireless channel is only effects individual pixel. The lost pixels at the receiver side can be recovered by using Boundary Interpolation (BI) Algorithm using wavelet. The results showed that the New proposed algorithm boundary interpolation (BI) using wavelet with pixel interleaver is better in term of MSE and PSNR.

Keywords—Image Transmission, Wavelet, Pixel Interleaver, Boundary Interpolation Algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

OVER the last decade, wireless multimedia communication has attracted considerably interest by both researcher community and industry to address the increased demand for multimedia services over wireless networks communication. [1].The image is transmitted over the wireless channel block by block. Due to severe fading, entire image blocks can be lost. Lowers data transmission rates and can further increase the network congestion which can aggravate the burst bit error or packet loss. Instead, show that it is possible to satisfactorily reconstruct the lost pixel or lost blocks by using the available information surrounding them; In the image reconstruction algorithm, the block repair method is to carry out on spatial correlation property of the natural image. The interpolation method uses those belonging to surrounding Blocks to interpolate the missing blocks [2]. Traditional ways to deal with packet losses are either based on packet retransmissions such as Automatic repeat Request (ARQ) [3] or forward error correction (FEC). Image surveillance may not benefit from ARQ based error recovery since retransmissions cause additional delay and communication overhead.

On other hand, FEC based methods used to combat fading in the wireless channel is required to increase the channel bandwidth and power consumption.

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In this context, error concealment approach receiver's particular attention as an effective mechanism that reconstructs the distorted multimedia data as closely as the original one without increasing the bandwidth demand as well as avoiding the burden of retransmission and consequently delay.

II. PREVIOUS WORKS

Various image transmission works have been studied. Sh. D. Rane ,J. Remus and G.Sapiro, Method fails to reconstruct image features which are completely obliterated during transmission, and, at present, is not uniformly satisfactory for all diagonal edges. Slanting edges which deviate slightly from the horizontal and vertical directions are reconstructed properly. But, the algorithm has no specific solution for perfect diagonal edges, and such edges are not satisfactorily reconstructed at this low computational complexity. The reconstruction capability for larger block sizes used inJPEG2000 remains to be seen, and is a part of ongoing work [4]. Sh. D. Rane, G. Sapiro and M. Bertalmio, Compression ratio can be further increased by finding better masks by providing more image information. The missing blocks in the different channels need not be in the same image position, information from different channels can be used in the block classification and reconstruction. Adding this to the current neighboring information used is expected to improve even further the quality of the results [5].

Ch. Tang HSIEH, Y. Liang CHEN and Ch. Hsu HSU, Method is combined with the best neighborhood matching approach and the different frequency repair on wavelet domain to carry on the fast lost block Reconstruction, the method considers the relationship between the different frequency compositions and each layer of neighboring texture at the same time. Method is that the image wavelet dimension not only resolves the different frequency compositions but also provides three directive compositions [6].

S.Kother Mohideen, S. Arumuga Perumaland M. Mohamed Sathik image de-noising using discrete wavelet transform is analyzed. The experiments were conducted to study the suitability of different wavelet bases and also different window sizes. Among all discrete wavelet bases, coiflet performs well in image de-noising. Experimental results also show that modified Neighshrink gives better result than Neighshrink, Weiner filter and Visushrink.[7].

W. A. Mahmoud, M. S. Abdul-Wahab and A. Sabri, performance are examined in noisy environment. Without noise, and for BI algorithm, it can be concluded that the reconstruction is not good when using Daubchies and Biorthogonal wavelet basis function by using the human visual display.

This is because the Haar wavelet function has only two taps for the low and high frequency filters, while for Daubchies and Biorthogonal there are more than two taps for the two low and high frequency filters which make the pixel values distributed over more pixels not in the vicinity of the nearest pixels [8].

III. DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORM (DWT)

Wavelets are mathematical functions that dissect or analyze data into different frequency components so that each component may be studied with a scale-matched resolution [9]. For example, if a given signal is viewed through a large window, large features can be observed. If this signal is viewed through a small window, only small features can be observed. Wavelets provide some advantages over Fourier transforms in a number of areas, including the analysis of physical situations where the signal contains discontinuities and sharp spikes. Wavelets were developed independently in the fields of mathematics, quantum physics, electrical engineering, and Seismic geology and can be used in applications such as image compression, turbulence, human vision, radar and earthquake prediction [9]. The term wavelet refers to a set of orthonormal basis functions that are created by dilation and translation of scaling function and a mother wavelet function. The finite scale multi-resolution representation of a discrete function can be described as a Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) [10]. DWT is a fast linear operation via a data vector, whose length is an integer power of two. The scaling function for multiresolution approximation can be obtained as the a two-scale dilatational equation

$$\phi(x) = \sum_k a_L(k)\phi(2x-k) \quad (1)$$

For some suitable sequence of coefficients. Once has been found, an associated mother wavelet is given by similar looking formula.

$$\psi(x) = \sum_k a_H(k)\phi(2x-k) \quad (2)$$

Wavelet analysis leads to perfect reconstruction filter banks using the coefficient sequences and. The input sequence is convolved with high-pass filter (HPF) and low-pass filter (LPF) and are downsampled the results by two, yielding the transform signals and. The signal is reconstructed through upsampling and convolution with high and low synthesis filters and. By cascading the analysis filter bank with itself a number of times, digital signal decomposition with dyadic frequency scaling known as DWT can be formed. The DWT for any image as a 2-D signal can be derived from 1-D DWT. The easiest way for obtaining scaling and wavelet function for two dimensions is by multiplying two 1-D functions. The scaling function for 2-D DWT can be obtained by multiplying two 1-D scaling functions: representing the approximation subband image (LL). The analysis filter bank for a single level 2-D DWT structure produces the detailed subband images (HL, LH, HH) corresponding to three different to three different directional-orientations (Horizontal, Vertical and

Diagonal) and a lower resolution subband image LL. The filter bank structure cab be iterated in a similar manner on the LL channel to provide multilevel decomposition [3].

IV. PROPOSED IMAGE TRANSMISSION MODEL

In this section, describe the assumptions consider for the research. The impacts of noise can damage entire blocks of the image, when such images are transmitted over fading channels. The communication modle used in the simulations are given in this section. The proposal algorithms for reconstruction of lost blocks in wireless image transmission using Boundary Interpolation (BI) using wavelet, Boundary Interpolation (BI) using wavelet with Paxil interleaver, The input image transmitted by transmitter device and through fading channel to receiver side, the effects of fading damage entire blocks of the image in different sizes. After received image, the lost blocks in wireless image are reconstructed by one of proposed algorithms. As shown in the figure 1.

Fig. 1 Proposed model BI using wavelet with pixel interleaver

A. Pixel Interleaver

Pixel Interleaving is a technique that takes pixel from a fixed produces the identical pixel at the output in a different temporal order and technique The interleaver rearranges input pixel such that consecutive pixel are spaced apart. At the receiver end, the interleaved pixel is arranged back into the original sequence by the Deinterleaver [12]. As a result of interleaving, correlated pixel introduced in the transmission channel appears to be statistically independent at the receiver and thus allows distributing the image pixel [11]. Figure 2.

Illustrates block of image such sets of interrelated lost block events.

A Random interleaver is one with a randomly generated mapping between input pixel and output pixel position, that is, for an interleaver of length L. Where L equal the image size (n*m), the input sequence is a scrambled according to pseudo-random number set to form output sequence where L = m*n, m equal to row and equal column. The advantage of random interleaver is their ease of generation, but the disadvantage is that it is not possible to guarantee the minimum spreading properties. Random interleaver tends to have very low s-parameters and very high dispersion.

Fig. 2 Pixel image interleaver

B. BI Algorithm using wavelet

The BI Algorithm using wavelet is utilized to reconstruct lost block due to wireless channel fading. The BI Algorithm using wavelet is given as

- 1) The nearest row above the lost block will be taken (which has the same size of the column of the lost block, i.e., $1 \times B$) as shown in Figure 3, denoted as N.
- 2) The nearest row below the lost block will be taken (which has the same size of the column of the lost block, i.e., $1 \times B$) as shown in Figure 3, denoted as S.
- 3) The nearest column to the right of the lost block will be taken (which has the same size of the row of the lost block, i.e., $B \times 1$) as shown in Figure 3, denoted as E.
- 4) The nearest column to the left of the lost block will be taken (which has the same size of the row of the lost block, i.e., $B \times 1$) as shown in Figure 3, denoted as W.
- 5) The 1-D discrete wavelet transform for all the surrounding will be obtained. This gives the approximate (low frequency components) and detail (high frequency components) coefficients. Each has a dimension equals to one-half of its original size, i.e., $B/2$.
- 6) The values of the detail coefficients are translated as additional elements in their approximate elements with each of the new low frequency components having dimension of B.
- 7) N_{nd} , S_{nd} , E_{nd} , and W_{nd} have been given zero values and all are vectors of length B.
- 8) By taking the 1-D inverse discrete wavelet transform for the new values of approximation and detail coefficients give the new values of N, S, E, and W which is of size of $2B$.
- 9) Downsample the new values of N, S, E, and W.

10) Now start reconstructing the lost block according to the following Equation:

$$R_{(m,m)} = \frac{N_{(m)} + W_{(n)} + S_{(B-M+1)} + E_{(B-n+1)}}{2} \quad (3)$$

Where $m = 1 \dots B$ and $n = 1 \dots B$

Fig. 3 the Demonstration of N, S, E, and W

C. Image quality metrics

In this research, two image quality metrics as performance criteria are used to show the lost block effect on the transmitted image through wireless communication system. Mean Square Error MSE is the simplest implementation to measure the image quality by averaging the squared intensity differences of image after reconstruction and reference image. The image quality is measured as the MSE value which is defined as

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N \times M} \sum_i^N \sum_j^M [I(i, j) - \hat{I}(i, j)]^2 \quad (4)$$

Where, $N \times M$ is the number of pixels in the image $I(i, j)$ and $\hat{I}(i, j)$ are the pixel value of reconstructed image. Peak Signal to Noise Ratio PSNR, describes the ratio between the maximum possible power of a signal and the power of noise. PSNR is usually expressed in terms of the logarithmic decibel:

$$PSNR(db) = 20 \log \frac{2^f - 1}{MSE} \quad (5)$$

Where f is the largest possible value of the image ($f = 8$ i.e. $2^f - 1 = 255$) for grayscale images. Scale Structural Similarity (SSIM) is a relatively new method by which it is possible to measure the similarity between two images, it is calculated from three image measurement comparisons: luminance, contrast, and structure. Each of these measures is calculated over an 8×8 local square window, which moves pixel-by-pixel over the entire image. At each step, the local statistics and SSIM index are calculated within the local window [13]. The resulting SSIM index map often exhibits undesirable 'blocking' artifacts; each window is filtered with a Gaussian weighting function (11×11 pixels). In practice, a single overall quality measure of the entire image is usually required and so the mean SSIM index is calculated in order to evaluate the overall image quality.

The SSIM can be considered to represent a quality measure of one of the images being compared, where the other image is considered to be of optimum quality. It can deliver results between 0 and 1, where 1 represents excellent quality and 0 represents poor quality. The MSSIM method, similar to SSIM, is a convenient way to incorporate image details at different resolutions. This approach is image synthesis-based and aids calibration of the parameters, such as viewing distance, that affect the relative importance between differing scales.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, present experimental results and performance evaluation of the investigation schemes in the terms of MSR, PSNR and MSSIM. The Lena image 512*512 grayscale is used as test image. In the first experiments, compare the performance of all investigated schemes for varying number of lost blocks at different positions on the test image. The transmission image protocol is governing the sender to send each 8x8 pixels at once. The first scenario, supposed there are five lost blocks 8x8 pixel in test image due to wireless channel effects as shown in the figure 4. The proposed BI algorithm used wavelet and other proposed BI algorithm used wavelet and pixel interleaver approaches are applied on the test image to enhance the image quality at receiver side. The simulation results indicate the superior performance of BI algorithm used wavelet with pixel interleaver. The pixel interleave is distributing the lost block 8x8 pixels to all parts of image.

Fig. 4 Received image with 5 blocks lost 8x8 pixels

The BI used wavelet with pixel interleave applied on lost pixel rather than lost block. The results of reconstructed images at the receive side are shown in Figure 5. The percentage of matching by the observes has been parented ad image reconstruction equality by human observer.

BI algorithm used wavelet BI algorithm used wavelet with pixel interleaver
 Fig. 5 Reconstructed image with 5 blocks lost 8x8 pixels

Table I Show the MSE, PSNR and MSSIM values (dB) of the simulation results for the reconstructed image. However, the value of MSE is reduced by using BI algorithm used wavelet with Pixel interleaver. The value of PSNR of BI algorithm used wavelet with Pixel interleaver is found better as compared to BI algorithm used wavelet only. The different between two algorithms are very low in terms of MSSIM.

TABLE I
 COMPARISON BETWEEN ALGORITHM IN TERMS OG MSE, PSNR AND MSSIM

Algorithm	MSE	PSNR	MSSIM
BI Algorithm used Wavelet	1.130	47.596	0.9990
BI Algorithm used Wavelet with Interleaver	0.790	49.154	0.9981

Second scenario is supposed there are ten lost blocks 8x8 at different locations in the test image as show in figure 6.

Figure 7 presents the images after applying the two algorithms. This figure shows that the perefomance BI alorhtim used wavelet with pixels interleaver is the better to reconstruction lost blocks. Table 2 shows the comparison for both algorithms. Low MSE value and high PSNR value are obtained from BI algorithm used wavelet with Pixels interleaver.

Fig. 6 Received image with 10 blocks lost 8x8 pixels

BI algorithm used wavelet BI algorithm used wavelet with pixel interleaver
 Fig. 7 Reconstructed image with 5 blocks lost 8x8 pixels

TABLE II
 COMPARISON BETWEEN ALGORITHMS IN TERMS OF MSE, PSNR AND MSSIM

Algorithm	MSE	PSNR	MSSIM
BI Algorithm used Wavelet	2.374	44.374	0.997
BI Algorithm used Wavelet with Interleaver	1.545	46.238	0.996

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a algorithms to reconstructed the image has lost blocks due to multipath wireless channel. The simulation results shows that the proposed BI algorithm used wavelet with pixel interleaver is higher capable to reconstructed images and give superior significant gain in term of MSE and PSNR

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